

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC NUCLEI. PART VI*. BROMINATION OF ARYL ESTERS OF *m*-CRESOTIC ACID

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Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl, *m*-, *p*-nitrophenyl and β -naphthyl esters of *m*-cresotic acid have been brominated and their bromo derivatives obtained and the constitution of the compounds, so prepared, confirmed.

Bromination of phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl, *m*-, *p*-nitrophenyl and β -naphthyl esters of *m*-cresotic acid has been described. In the case of all other esters except β -naphthyl ester, mono- and dibromo derivatives are obtained by the action of bromine in acetic acid solution, but β -naphthyl ester gives only monobromo derivative in a pure state. Use of liquid bromine gives tribromo compounds in the case of phenyl and *m*-cresyl esters, whilst only the dibromo derivatives of *o*- and *p*-cresyl esters can give the tribromo compounds with liquid bromine. The presence of the NO₂ group in the nitrophenyl esters so completely deactivates the molecule that even with liquid bromine, no bromine can enter the phenolic nucleus. The constitutions of these compounds have been proved by their hydrolysis and confirmed by their preparation by condensing the requisite phenol with the requisite acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monobromo Derivatives.—Solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (16 c.c. of 20%) was gradually added to the simple ester (4 g.) already dissolved in glacial acetic acid at room temperature, but in the case of nitrophenyl esters, hot solutions were used. The mixture was then shaken for some time when a crystalline bromo derivative separated from the solution. All monobromo derivatives were crystallised from acetic acid. These are described in Table I.

Dibromo Derivatives.—The ester (2 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid, was heated on a boiling water-bath with bromine solution (4 g. dissolved in 5 c.c. of acetic acid) for about 3 to 4 hours. The bromo derivative separated on cooling; In the case of nitrophenyl esters, however, action of liquid bromine on the ester directly at room temperature, gave better yields. The reaction mixture after some time was diluted with water and excess of bromine removed with sodium bisulphite. They all were crystallised from acetic acid. These are described in Table II.

Tribromo Derivatives.—Liquid bromine (10 g.) was added to phenyl or *m*-cresyl ester (4 g.) whilst liquid bromine (5 g.) was added to the dibromo derivative of *o*- or *p*-cresyl ester (5 g.) and the reaction mixture was shaken at room temperature for about an hour and then diluted with water. Excess of bromine was removed by the addition of sodium bisulphite to it and then the product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The substances are described in Table III.

Hydrolysis.—The hydrolysis of mono and dibromo derivatives was carried out by boiling under reflux the compound with excess of 5% solution of sodium hydroxide for about 3-4 hours. Carbon dioxide was then passed through the cold solution, when the phenolic component separated. This was removed by ether extraction and the aqueous layer gave on acidification with hydrochloric acid, the acid component. The acids were crystallised from acetic acid. They as well as the phenolic components were identified by mixed m.p. with authentic specimens.

In the case of tribromo derivatives, however, they were boiled with 8% solution of sodium hydroxide for about 5 hours and the two components were separated and identified in the same way as above.

*The previous part of the series, published in the Nov. issue of this Journal (1940) should be read be as Part V and not as Part IV as printed.

Preparation of Bromo Derivatives by Condensation.—The monobromo compounds were prepared by heating together for about half an hour 6-bromo-*m*-cresotic acid (4 g.), requisite phenol (3 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (2.5 c.c.) at 120-125° in the case of phenol and cresols and at 130-135° in the case of nitrophenols and β -naphthol. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and the solid was washed with dilute alkali. It was crystallised from acetic acid and mixed melting point was taken with the corresponding bromination product, when no lowering was observed.

Dibromo derivatives were similarly obtained from 2 : 6-dibromo-*m*-cresotic acid (4 g.), phenol or cresol (3 g.) or nitrophenol (2 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (2.5 c.c.) and identified, and tribromo compounds from 2 : 6-dibromo-*m*-cresotic acid (4 g.), *p*-bromophenol, *p*-bromo-*o*-cresol or *p*-bromo-*m*-cresol (2.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (2.5 c.c.) by heating together at 130-135° for about an hour and worked up and identified as above.

TABLE I
B stands for bromobenzoate.

Name of the compounds.	M. p.	Formula.	% Bromine	
			Found.	Calc.
Phenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	108-7°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	25.9	26.0
<i>o</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	108-9°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	24.8	24.9
<i>m</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	90-9°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	25.0	24.9
<i>p</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	106-6°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	24.7	24.9
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	147-48°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ NBr	23.0	22.7
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	175-78°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ NBr	22.8	22.7
β -Naphthyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-B	143-44°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br	22.5	22.4

TABLE II
DB-stands for dibromobenzoate.

Name of the compounds.	M. p.	Formula.	% Bromine	
			Found.	Calc.
Phenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	126-27°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ Br ₂	41.8	41.5
<i>o</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	167-68°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	40.2	40.0
<i>m</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	126-27°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	39.9	40.0
<i>p</i> -Cresyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	129-30°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂	40.2	40.0
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	186-89°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₃ NBr ₂	38.2	38.4
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-DB	212-20°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₃ NBr ₂	38.3	38.4

TABLE III

Name of the compounds.	M. p.	Formula.	% Bromine	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-dibromobenzoate	179-80°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ Br ₃	52.0	51.8
2-Methyl-4-bromophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-dibromobenzoate	182-83°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br ₃	50.0	50.1
3-Methyl-4-bromophenyl 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-dibromobenzoate	157-58°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br ₃	49.6	50.1
4-Methyl-2-bromophenyl-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 5-dibromobenzoate	189-90°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br ₃	50.0	50.1

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Received November 28, 1946.